

B Appendix: Storyboards Design

B.1 Experimental Design Overview

Privacy Negotiation Routes
R1: Tenant Initiated – Monetary Compensation – Acceptance
R2: Tenant Initiated – Monetary Compensation – Declination
R3: Tenant Initiated – Physical Adjustment – Acceptance
R4: Tenant Initiated – Physical Adjustment – Declination
R5: Host Initiated – Monetary Compensation – Acceptance
R6: Host Initiated – Monetary Compensation – Declination
R7: Host Initiated – Physical Adjustment – Acceptance
R8: Host Initiated – Physical Adjustment – Declination

Table 2: Summary of the eight privacy negotiation routes, categorized by Privacy Negotiation Initiator (tenant initiated vs. host initiated), Privacy Negotiation Strategy (monetary compensation vs. physical adjustment), and Outcome (acceptance vs. declination).

B.2 Manipulation Check

Figure 3: Distribution of perceived realism responses across three device contexts. Participants indicated whether they had experienced similar situations and whether they could imagine them occurring. Blue segments represent participants who perceived the scenarios as realistic (experienced and/or can imagine), while red segments represent participants who did not (neither experienced nor can imagine). Across all three device contexts, most participants perceived the scenarios as realistic: 94.7% for Driveway Camera, 83.0% for Video Conferencing Device for TVs, and 88.3% for Smart Display Device.